

CREATION OF MOBILE APPLICATION OF BUSINESS DIRECTORY OF SERVICE FACILITIES IN NUKUS CITY

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Abstract. Today, with the advent of mobile technology, businesses have more speed than mobile apps can offer in helping businesses. Business directories of service facilities, offering a variety of services, have become a means to facilitate the acceptance and use of this important introduction by customers. Therefore, a mobile application for service facilities in Nukus will help businesses reach their capacity and provide access to services.

Key words: Mobile application development, Business catalog, Service objects Nukus city, Mobile app features, User interface design, User experience (UX), Marketing and advertising, Customer engagement, Data management and updates.

СОЗДАНИЕ МОБИЛЬНОГО ПРИЛОЖЕНИЯ БИЗНЕС-СПРАВОЧНИКА ОБЪЕКТОВ СФЕРЫ ОБСЛУЖИВАНИЯ Г. НУКУСА

Аннотация. Сегодня, с появлением мобильных технологий, у бизнеса больше скорости, чем могут предложить мобильные приложения, помогающие бизнесу. Бизнес-справочники предприятий обслуживания, предлагающих разнообразные услуги, стали средством, облегчающим принятие и использование клиентами этого важного введения. Поэтому мобильное приложение для объектов обслуживания в Нукусе поможет предприятиям выйти на свои мощности и предоставит доступ к услугам.

Ключевые слова: Разработка мобильных приложений, Бизнес-каталог, Объекты обслуживания г. Нукус, Возможности мобильного приложения, Дизайн пользовательского интерфейса, Пользовательский опыт (UX), Маркетинг и реклама, Взаимодействие с клиентами, Управление данными и обновления.

INTRODUCTION: This article examines the importance and necessity of creating a mobile application for a business directory of service facilities in Nukus. Mobile applications, while offering many opportunities in the field of management and marketing, help the service facilities business catalogs to have a good impact on average customers.

1. Change of business catalogs of service objects

Business directory of service facilities, various features of service facilities, along with address and contact information, gives them the opportunity to familiarize themselves with related services. As a result, service objects can be quickly and easily found and known by average customers and potential customers.

2. Importance of mobile applications

Mobile applications are programs with structural and functional conveniences that are widely read by active customers. Their consumption through mobile devices helps to attract customers to service facilities and offer them related services. Mobile applications make it easier for service facilities to use the opportunities provided, to implement advertising and marketing campaigns, to meet the needs of customers and to provide them with high-quality services. [1.86]

3. Service facilities in the city of Nukus

The city of Nukus is enriched with many service facilities such as tourism, restaurants, service centers, cafes, etc. These facilities are engaged in offering various services, selling products and instructions, providing affordable services and offering quality public services. It should include a mobile application of service facilities, customer convenience, ease of delivery and information.

4. Creation of a mobile application

The process of creating a mobile application for a business directory of service facilities in Nukus will consist of initial concept, prototype creation and testing, and finalization. In the process of creating an application, developers can use mobile application platforms, and information related to design, user interface, functions and service objects is collected.

5. Mobile application success and reinforcement

After the mobile application is created, it is important to test it, discuss its possibilities with potential customers and users, get their feedback and improve it. Mobile application maintenance should be done through regular communication, updates and checks with requirements and display objects. [2.65]

Creating a mobile application of the business directory of service facilities in Nukus will make it easier to deliver service facilities to customers, provide complete services together with them, and satisfy the needs of customers. A business catalog of service facilities through a mobile application helps to increase competition in the service industry and attract new customers. This application provides great opportunities for service facilities and convenience for users. It also makes it easier for customers to access applications through their mobile devices, speeding up their use of services.

We can make the following recommendations to make significant progress in the process of creating a mobile application of the business directory of service facilities in Nukus:

At the beginning, it will be appropriate to analyze the public requirements and the wishes of the authorized customers in the field of services throughout the city of Nukus by conducting an analysis and research. It is necessary to create a user-friendly and intuitive interface in the mobile application. Such an interface makes the application easy to use and helps users quickly find the services they want. Service objects must have a place in the application. Full and direct information about the details, addresses, contact information and services of such facilities should be easily found in the application. [3.47]

In order to successfully implement application prototyping and testing processes, it is important to conduct validation processes with users and potential customers. Listening to their interests, requirements and suggestions is important for improving the quality and usability of the application.

In order to ensure the correct communication between the service objects and the mobile application, the objects are expected to update, offer services and update the application. This is highly important for app users to use new services and attract customers. The mobile application of the business directory of service objects facilitates the process of establishing relations between objects and customers and the full provision of services. In addition, facilities will be able to use the application to advertise their services, offer discounts and bonuses, or establish average relationships with customers.

Creating a mobile application of a business directory of service facilities in Nukus will bring many benefits for facilities. Through this application, they find an easier way to sell objects, services and products. Customers can quickly and easily find service facilities, get information about services and be offered related discounts and benefits using the mobile application.

Guide and recommendations

In the process of creating a mobile application of the business directory of service facilities in the city of Nukus, it is important to follow the following guidelines and recommendations: [5.79]

When creating a service facility business directory mobile application, focus on performing analysis and research on relationships between facilities and customers. Understanding the object's service interests, requirements, and requests for rendering objects will be of great importance in achieving the user-friendliness and usability of the application. [6.103]

The app should focus on user-friendliness and ease of use. Intuitive interface, navigation that helps to find the right way and easy-to-use functions play an important role in making the application convenient and interesting for users. Information, addresses, contact information and services of service facilities must be completely and correctly indicated in the application. Information about facilities is accurate and updates should be taken seriously. If the object's information is not updated in time, the application will not be reliable and user-friendly. Therefore, facilities must carry with them constant updating of their information and the services they are able to provide. When creating a mobile application of a business directory of service objects, marketing and advertising should be given important attention to allow users and potential customers to familiarize themselves with the application. Facilities should be fully prepared for the app, such as having their services and discounts displayed on the app, and promoting the app through advertising and marketing campaigns. [3.98]

In the process of developing a mobile application, it is important to consult with users and customers, listen to their suggestions and apply them. Users' opinions and suggestions will be of great importance for updating and improving the application. Provide them with questionnaires, feedback options, and easy ways for them to leave their opinions. The mobile application should allow users to search for service objects, find out, order and use discounts. In this direction, a convenient interface, easy-to-use functions, correct information and updates are of great importance in the application.

CONCLUSION: It is also important to develop a targeted marketing strategy for the mobile application of the service facilities business directory. Popularity of the application with mass speed, the use of advertising and marketing campaigns to attract customers, activity in social networks and the use of dating tools, cooperation with objects will be of great importance.

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